

Supplementary Materials for:
Inference of Phylogenetic Networks
from Sequence Data using Composite Likelihood

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S1 Comparative performance of PhyNEST with other methods on data generated under the Jukes-Cantor model

In this section, we used simulations to examine whether PHYNEST can return networks that are competitive in terms of topological accuracy and computational efficiency compared to SNAQ [Solís-Lemus and Ané, 2016], implemented in the Julia package PHYLONETWORKS [Solís-Lemus et al., 2017], and the `InferNetwork.MPL` function, implemented in PHYLONET [Than et al., 2008, Yu and Nakhleh, 2015] (hereafter referred to as SNAQ and PHYLONET, respectively). The simulations generally followed the procedure described in the main text section, ‘Comparative performance of PHYNEST with other methods’, unless otherwise mentioned. Note that the computational times reported for PHYNEST in this section are longer than those in the main text, because the results reported here are for an earlier version of PHYNEST (v. 0.1.0). The updated version of PHYNEST used for the analyses in the main text (v. 0.1.11) includes several algorithmic updates that improved computation times.

Fig. S1: Two hybridization scenarios were used: a) \mathcal{N}_1 and b) \mathcal{N}_2 . Edge lengths are in coalescent units and are noted below each tree edge (black). Inheritance probabilities are indicated beside each reticulation edge (teal and light blue).

We used two species network topologies, \mathcal{N}_1 and \mathcal{N}_2 (Fig. S1a and S1b, respectively). We simulated $g = \{50, 200, 500, 1000, 3000, 5000\}$ and $g = \{40, 200, 500, 1000, 3000, 5000\}$ gene trees, for \mathcal{N}_1 and \mathcal{N}_2 , respectively. For each locus, we generated a multiple sequence alignment of 250 b.p. under the Jukes-Cantor (JC69) model [Jukes and Cantor, 1969] using SEQ-GEN [Rambaut and Grass, 1997], followed by the estimation of an unrooted gene tree using IQ-TREE [Nguyen et al., 2015] with the evolutionary model specified as JC69. Using the set of g estimated gene trees, we computed quartet concordance factors (CFs) using PHYLONETWORKS as input for network inference with SNAQ. All gene trees are then rooted

using the true outgroup for input into PHYLONET. A single alignment in sequential PHYLIP format for PHYNEST was created.

Using the prepared input files, we estimated the network using SNAQ, PHYLONET, and PHYNEST, employing both the hill climbing and simulated annealing searching algorithms (hereafter referred to as PHYNEST_HC and PHYNEST_SA, respectively), with 10 independent searches each. The starting topology, randomly selected from the set of estimated gene trees, for SNAQ and PHYNEST, was modified using Nearest Neighbor Interchange rearrangement in each independent run. For PHYNEST_SA, we set $\alpha = c = 0.25$. Again, the results presented in this section were obtained using PHYNEST version 0.1.0, and the number of steps allowed in the simulated annealing search was limited. We acknowledge this limitation and conducted an entirely new simulation study that allowed a larger number of steps during the search and reported the results in the main text. Nevertheless, the results reported here are informative about the method’s performance under the JC69 model, although the search could have been more thorough.

The accuracy of the estimated network obtained from each method was assessed by measuring the dissimilarity between the true and estimated networks using tree-, cluster-, and tripartition-based dissimilarity metrics, implemented in PHYLONET command `Charnet`. For all three metrics, the estimated network is topologically closer to the true network when the dissimilarity metric is closer to zero. We also recorded the time taken for gene tree estimation using IQ-TREE and the running time for each analysis. We conducted 100 replicates for each g , although analyses failed to complete in one of the 100 replicates when $g = 1000$ and 5000 , and in two of the 100 replicates when $g = 3000$ for \mathcal{N}_2 due to excessively long computation times.

Fig. S2: Summary of the running time (y-axis; in hours and log-scaled) for the four methods evaluated: PHYLONET, SNAQ, PHYNEST using hill climbing PHYNEST_HC, and simulated annealing (PHYNEST_SA). The results are based on simulated data for the hybridization scenarios (a) \mathcal{N}_1 and (b) \mathcal{N}_2 , over various numbers of loci (x-axis).

Figure S2a summarizes the running time for each replicate for the different values of g for \mathcal{N}_1 . All four methods tested showed generally consistent running times across different values of g . PHYLONET was the fastest, taking approximately 25 seconds on average, followed by SNAQ at approximately 45 seconds on average. PHYNEST_HC required approximately 7 minutes for computation, while PHYNEST_SA took approximately 4 hours. Figure S3a summarizes the time required for gene tree estimation for different values of g using IQ-TREE for \mathcal{N}_1 . The estimation of a single gene tree took approximately 94 seconds on average, which accumulated with increasing g and ranged from approximately 77 minutes when $g = 50$ to approximately 130 hours when $g = 5000$. Parsing the input alignments for PHYNEST required less than 1 minute.

Figure S2b summarizes the running time for each replicate across different g evaluated for \mathcal{N}_2 . Similar to \mathcal{N}_1 , the computation times were consistent regardless of g , taking < 10 minutes for SNAQ and PHYLONET, and approximately 100 minutes and 110 hours on average for PHYNEST_HC and PHYNEST_SA, respectively. Figure S3b summarizes the time required for gene tree estimation with different g using IQ-TREE for \mathcal{N}_2 . Estimating a single gene tree took approximately 120 seconds on average, which accumulated with increasing g , ranging from approximately 61 minutes when $g = 40$ to approximately 150 hours when $g = 5000$. Parsing the input alignments for PHYNEST took only a few minutes.

Fig. S3: Summary of the time taken for gene tree estimation (y-axis) using IQ-TREE across different numbers of loci (x-axis), based on simulated data for the hybridization scenarios (a) \mathcal{N}_1 and (b) \mathcal{N}_2 .

The tree- and cluster-based dissimilarity metrics (Fig. S4a and S4b, respectively) show that PHYNEST performed very well in reconstructing the true network when $g > 500$. It was not uncommon for PHYLONET and SNAQ to estimate networks that were distant from the true network when $g = 50$. This pattern disappeared for SNAQ as g was increased, but persisted for PHYLONET even when $g = 3000$. Based on the tripartition-based dissimilarity metric (Fig. S4c), all methods suffered when $g < 3000$, except for SNAQ which reconstructed

the true network most frequently when $g = 3000$. When $g = 5000$, all methods almost always correctly identified the true relationships.

Although the assessment of each method based on the three metrics generally followed similar patterns, we question the utility of the tree- and cluster-based dissimilarity metrics as they seem excessively liberal, yielding a dissimilarity of zero even when the two topologies being compared are not isomorphic. For example, tree- and cluster-based dissimilarities of zero were computed when a network where species 5 is the hybrid of species 4 and the common ancestor of species 4 and 3, which can be written as

$$(1, (2, ((3, (4, (5)\#H)), \#H)));$$

is compared with \mathcal{N}_1 . In this network case, the hybrid taxon is incorrectly identified and has a different biological interpretation than that in \mathcal{N}_1 . We suspect this is due to the fact that the set of displayed trees for both networks is the same. Acknowledging the limitation of the tree- and cluster-based dissimilarity metrics used in this simulation study, we use the hardwired clustering dissimilarity measure in our new simulation study presented in the main text.

Fig. S4: Comparison of methods (x-axis) with respect to the topological accuracy (left y-axis) using simulated data using \mathcal{N}_1 . The data were generated under JC69, and accuracy was measured using the (a) tree-, (b) cluster-, and (c) tripartition-based dissimilarity metrics over various numbers of loci (gray boxes on right). Each dot represents one of 100 replicates made for each locus size using one of four methods. The points are jittered horizontally within each method and setting for ease of interpretation.

Fig. S5: Comparison of methods (x-axis) with respect to network topological accuracy (left y-axis) using simulated data using \mathcal{N}_2 . The data were generated under JC69, and accuracy was measured using the (a) tree-, (b) cluster-, and (c) tripartition-based dissimilarity metrics over various numbers of loci (gray boxes on right). Each dot represents one of 100 replicates for each locus size using one of four methods. The points are jittered horizontally within each method and setting for ease of interpretation.

Figures S5a and S5b present the tree- and cluster-based dissimilarity, respectively, between the estimated and true networks for each replicate across different g for \mathcal{N}_2 . Focusing on the tripartition-based dissimilarity metric in Figure S5c, the frequency of reconstructing the true network gradually increased with g for all methods. When $g = 5000$, PHYNEST_SA recovered the true network in every replicate.

S2 Modeling the ancestry of multiple lineages at a reticulation

For computational tractability, PHYNEST currently assumes a non-traditional coalescent model in which all lineages of a given locus must be inherited from the same parent at each reticulation vertex (i.e., the common inheritance model of [Fogg et al., 2023]; see Fig. S6). Here we examine the potential impact of this assumption by considering the frequency with which multiple lineages may reach a reticulation vertex.

Fig. S6: Common vs. independent inheritance for a 5-tip species network with one reticulation. (a) The network. (b, c) The two trees displayed by the network, each obtained by removing one reticulation edge. Expected site-pattern probabilities are computed as a mixture of loci generated by one or the other of these displayed trees, chosen for each locus according to an inheritance parameter. (d, e, f) Three of the many possible coalescent histories compatible with the network; the histories shown all contain pairs of lineages that enter the reticulation vertex from below and do not coalesce until they have exited it via the parental reticulation edges. In histories like (d) and (e), all lineages exiting the reticulation vertex go into the same parental edge (“common inheritance”). However, histories of the form (f) cannot arise on either of the two displayed trees and thus do not contribute to the site pattern probability calculations under the common inheritance model. This omission causes our site pattern probabilities to be biased relative to those expected under the “independent inheritance” model.

We considered the probability that a sample of n lineages would coalesce to a most recent common ancestor (MRCA) within an interval of a specific length, t . These probabilities are shown in Figure S7 for coalescent times ranging from 0.1 to 4.0. In Table S1, we also provide numerical values for four choices of coalescent time. This probability increases as the coalescent time increases; that is, for longer branches separating the reticulation vertex and the first divergence time below the reticulation vertex, it becomes increasingly likely that the lineages will have reached their MRCA prior to the reticulation event. This occurs for the majority of genes once the length of the interval exceeds 1.5 coalescent unit for all of the values of n we considered. When the number of lineages sampled is smaller, this is even more likely.

Fig. S7: The probability that a sample of n lineages would coalesce to a most recent common ancestor (MRCA; y-axis) within an interval of a specific length or time, t (x-axis), measured in coalescent units.

Table S1: Numerical values of the probability that a sample of n lineages would coalesce within the four choices of interval or time, t , measured in coalescent units.

	$t = 0.5$	$t = 1.0$	$t = 1.5$	$t = 2.0$
$n = 2$	0.3935	0.6321	0.7769	0.8647
$n = 3$	0.2018	0.4731	0.6709	0.7982
$n = 4$	0.1214	0.3871	0.6095	0.7589
$n = 5$	0.0813	0.3341	0.5695	0.7329

Thus, while this assumption is not likely to present a major issue for many of the datasets for which it will be used, we acknowledge this caveat of the model, and note that it is likely to be more problematic when the interval between the divergence event and the reticulation is shorter and when the number of lineages sampled in the hybrid species is larger.

S3 Non-identifiability of the timing of reticulation events

Under the common inheritance model of [Fogg et al., 2023], which is the model underlying the current version of PHYNEST, only two of the following three times are identifiable: the age of the “left” parent, the age of the “right” parent, and the age of the reticulation vertex. We provide a short proof below. PHYNEST thus sets the time of the reticulation event to be equal to the age of the “younger” parent (i.e., the parent whose age is smaller).

Proof of non-identifiability of the time of reticulation vertices: Consider a reticulation event as depicted in Figure 1c in the main text. In addition to the times noted in

Figure 1c, let τ_ρ denote the time of the root node, and let τ_φ denote the time of the reticulation. Here we suppose that τ_φ can differ from τ_3 (note that in a time-consistent network, $\tau_\varphi = \tau_2 = \tau_3$). Under the common inheritance model, this network can be decomposed into two displayed trees. The first displayed tree, which occurs with probability γ , is given by $(a:\tau_\rho, (b:\tau_2, (c:\tau_1, d:\tau_1):\tau_2 - \tau_1):\tau_\rho - \tau_2)$, as shown in Figure 1b. The second displayed tree, which occurs with probability $1 - \gamma$, is given by $((a:\tau_3, b:\tau_3):\tau_\rho - \tau_3, (c:\tau_1, d:\tau_1):\tau_\rho - \tau_1)$, as shown in Figure 1a. Sequence data are assumed to arise along the displayed trees according to a specified substitution model (here, the JC69 model). Note, however, that neither displayed tree includes the parameter τ_φ and thus the time of the reticulation vertex is not recoverable from the data.

S4 The relationships of the 15 site pattern frequencies for 24 permutations of four taxa

Table S2: The relationships of the 15 site pattern frequencies for 24 permutations of four taxa $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$. The observed site pattern frequencies for the $4! = 24$ different permutations of the four sequences are generated by permuting the 15 site pattern frequencies of one quartet to obtain the site patterns for the other 23 quartets.

i	j	k	l	p_{iiii}	p_{iiij}	p_{iiji}	p_{ijjj}	p_{ijjk}	p_{ijji}	p_{ijik}	p_{ijji}	p_{jiii}	p_{ijjk}	p_{kijk}	p_{jiki}	p_{jkii}	p_{ijkl}	
a	b	c	d	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
a	b	d	c	1	3	2	4	5	6	9	12	7	10	13	8	11	14	15
a	c	b	d	1	2	6	7	8	3	4	5	9	10	11	12	14	13	15
a	c	d	b	1	6	2	7	8	3	9	12	4	10	14	5	11	13	15
a	d	b	c	1	3	6	9	12	2	4	5	7	10	13	8	14	11	15
a	d	c	b	1	6	3	9	12	2	7	8	4	10	14	5	13	11	15
b	a	c	d	1	2	3	4	5	10	9	11	7	6	8	13	12	14	15
b	a	d	c	1	3	2	4	5	10	7	13	9	6	12	11	8	14	15
b	c	a	d	1	2	10	9	11	3	4	5	7	6	8	13	14	12	15
b	c	d	a	1	10	2	9	11	3	7	13	4	6	14	5	8	12	15
b	d	a	c	1	3	10	7	13	2	4	5	9	6	12	11	14	8	15
b	d	c	a	1	10	3	7	13	2	9	11	4	6	14	5	12	8	15
c	a	b	d	1	2	6	7	8	10	9	11	4	3	5	14	12	13	15
c	a	d	b	1	6	2	7	8	10	4	14	9	3	12	11	5	13	15
c	b	a	d	1	2	10	9	11	6	7	8	4	3	5	14	13	12	15
c	b	d	a	1	10	2	9	11	6	4	14	7	3	13	8	5	12	15
c	d	a	b	1	6	10	4	14	2	7	8	9	3	12	11	13	5	15
c	d	b	a	1	10	6	4	14	2	9	11	7	3	13	8	12	5	15
d	a	b	c	1	3	6	9	12	10	7	13	4	2	5	14	8	11	15
d	a	c	b	1	6	3	9	12	10	4	14	7	2	8	13	5	11	15
d	b	a	c	1	3	10	7	13	6	9	12	4	2	5	14	11	8	15
d	b	c	a	1	10	3	7	13	6	4	14	9	2	11	12	5	8	15
d	c	a	b	1	6	10	4	14	3	9	12	7	2	8	13	11	5	15
d	c	b	a	1	10	6	4	14	3	7	13	9	2	11	12	8	5	15

S5 Computing observed quartet site pattern probabilities

Following [Chifman and Kubatko, 2014] and [Chifman and Kubatko, 2015], there are $4^4 = 256$ possible site patterns for any quartet, and these patterns can be reduced to 15 unique site pattern probabilities under the JC69 model:

$$p = (p_{iiii}, p_{iiij}, p_{iiji}, p_{ijii}, p_{jiii}, p_{ijij}, p_{jiij}, p_{iijj}, p_{ijik}, p_{jiik}, p_{ijki}, p_{jiki}, p_{iijk}, p_{jkii}, p_{ijkl}), \quad (1)$$

where i, j, k , and l denote distinct nucleotide states. We define the weight (ω) for each element in (1) as a vector of integers. Each integer represents the number of occurrences of the specific site pattern in the 16×16 flattening matrix of quartet site patterns in the same order as in (1):

$$\omega = (4, 12, 12, 12, 12, 12, 12, 12, 24, 24, 24, 24, 24, 24, 24). \quad (2)$$

Let W_q represent a vector of length 15 that contains observed site pattern frequencies for a quartet q from the data and $(W_q)_j$ be an entry of the W_q that represents the observed frequency of the site pattern j (see ‘Computing the Composite Likelihood of a Network subsection in Methods’ subsection in the main text for formal definitions of W_q and $(W_q)_j$). Let ω_j be the weight of the site pattern j as appears in (2) and M be the total length of the alignment. Formulas for computing the observed site pattern frequencies in terms of the W_q and ω_j values for the symmetric and asymmetric quartets are given below. Note that under the JC69 model, (1) is reduced to nine and 11 unique site patterns in symmetric and asymmetric quartets, respectively.

symmetric quartet

$$\begin{aligned} p_{iiii} &= \frac{(W_q)_{iiii}}{\omega_{iiii} \times M} \\ p_{iiij} &= \frac{(W_q)_{iiij} + (W_q)_{iiji}}{(\omega_{iiij} + \omega_{iiji}) \times M} \\ p_{iijj} &= \frac{(W_q)_{iijj}}{\omega_{iijj} \times M} \\ p_{iijk} &= \frac{(W_q)_{iijk}}{\omega_{iijk} \times M} \\ p_{ijii} &= \frac{(W_q)_{ijii} + (W_q)_{jiii}}{(\omega_{ijii} + \omega_{jiii}) \times M} \\ p_{ijij} &= \frac{(W_q)_{ijij} + (W_q)_{ijji}}{(\omega_{ijij} + \omega_{ijji}) \times M} \\ p_{ijik} &= \frac{(W_q)_{ijik} + (W_q)_{jiiik} + (W_q)_{ijki} + (W_q)_{jiki}}{(\omega_{ijik} + \omega_{jiiik} + \omega_{ijki} + \omega_{jiki}) \times M} \\ p_{ijkl} &= \frac{(W_q)_{ijkl}}{\omega_{ijkl} \times M} \\ p_{jkii} &= \frac{(W_q)_{jkii}}{\omega_{jkii} \times M} \end{aligned}$$

asymmetric quartet

$$\begin{aligned} p_{iiii} &= \frac{(W_q)_{iiii}}{\omega_{iiii} \times M} \\ p_{iiij} &= \frac{(W_q)_{iiij} + (W_q)_{iiji}}{(\omega_{iiij} + \omega_{iiji}) \times M} \\ p_{iijj} &= \frac{(W_q)_{iijj}}{\omega_{iijj} \times M} \\ p_{iijk} &= \frac{(W_q)_{iijk}}{\omega_{iijk} \times M} \\ p_{ijii} &= \frac{(W_q)_{ijii}}{\omega_{ijii} \times M} \\ p_{ijij} &= \frac{(W_q)_{ijij} + (W_q)_{ijji}}{(\omega_{ijij} + \omega_{ijji}) \times M} \\ p_{ijik} &= \frac{(W_q)_{ijik} + (W_q)_{ijki}}{(\omega_{ijik} + \omega_{ijki}) \times M} \\ p_{ijkl} &= \frac{(W_q)_{ijkl}}{\omega_{ijkl} \times M} \\ p_{jiii} &= \frac{(W_q)_{jiii}}{\omega_{jiii} \times M} \\ p_{jiiik} &= \frac{(W_q)_{jiiik} + (W_q)_{jiki}}{(\omega_{jiiik} + \omega_{jiki}) \times M} \\ p_{jkii} &= \frac{(W_q)_{jkii}}{\omega_{jkii} \times M} \end{aligned}$$

S6 Heuristic moves

PHYNEST uses five moves with the relevant functions available in the Julia package PHYLONETWORKS [Solís-Lemus et al., 2017] to search the network space. The search begins with a starting tree or a network with h reticulations. The number of reticulations, h , must be equal to or less than h_{max} , the user-specified maximum (or expected) number of reticulations in the network. The input network should be within the class of level-1 and have at least one valid placement for the root using the user-specified outgroup. Any proposed network is checked to verify that it is also level-1, with $h \leq h_{max}$, and rooted using the outgroup. In case there is no valid placement for the root in a proposed network, the proposed network is rejected, and a new network is proposed by making a different move. The five moves are:

- (i) Nearest-neighbor interchange (NNI): Performed on a tree edge chosen uniformly at random, which exchanges the connectivity of the subnetworks on opposite sides of the chosen edge.
- (ii) Head move of a reticulation edge: Let the vertex v be chosen at random from the set of reticulation vertices, V_N , and denote the two incoming edges by e' and e'' . Define the inheritance probability assigned to e' as γ' and the inheritance probability assigned to e'' as γ'' (equivalent to $(1 - \gamma')$). Select either e' or e'' at random according to their inheritance probabilities. In other words, e' has a probability of γ' and e'' has a probability of γ'' of being selected. We call the selected reticulation edge e hereafter. Define a new vertex v' along a randomly chosen edge b (i.e., v' has in-degree one and out-degree one). The head of e is moved by replacing v with v' so that v' now has an in-degree of two and an out-degree of one (i.e., $v' \in V_N$). Node v is removed, and the incoming and outgoing edges to v are merged.
- (iii) Tail move of a reticulation edge: As in (ii), the reticulation vertex v is chosen at random, and one of the two incoming edges (e' and e'') associated with v is selected according to their inheritance probabilities. We call the selected reticulation edge e , which has v as its head and u as its tail. A new vertex u' is defined along a randomly chosen edge b (i.e., u' has in-degree one and out-degree one). The tail of e is moved by replacing u with u' so that u' has an in-degree of one and an out-degree of two (i.e., u' is a tree vertex). Node u is removed, and the incoming and outgoing edges to u are merged.
- (iv) Change the direction of a reticulation edge: As in (ii), a reticulation vertex v is chosen at random and one of the two incoming edges (e' and e'') associated with v is selected according to their inheritance probabilities. We call the selected reticulation edge $e = (u, v)$, which has v as its head and u as its tail. The direction of e is ‘flipped’ by switching u and v thus $e = (v, u)$. Now, u is a reticulation vertex and v is a tree vertex.
- (v) Insertion of a reticulation edge: When the number of reticulations is less than h_{max} , two tree edges, b_1 and b_2 , in the network are selected at random. Two vertices with in-degree one and out-degree one, u and v , are created on b_1 and b_2 , respectively. A reticulation edge $e = (u, v)$ with length equal to zero and γ drawn uniformly from $[0, 0.5)$ is created.

Since PHYNEST searches the space of semi-directed networks using the moves implemented in PHYLONETWORKS, it is not possible for the number of reticulations to decrease (i.e., removing a reticulation) during the search. [Linz and Wicke, 2023] recently showed that because of this, the space of level-1 networks with an arbitrary number of reticulations is not connected under the move set used in PHYLONETWORKS. While our implementation in PHYNEST requires the user to specify h_{max} and should always return a network with this number of reticulations, [Linz and Wicke, 2023] also show that the move set in PHYLONETWORKS is not connected even within a fixed number of reticulation vertices. The new move strategy proposed by [Linz and Wicke, 2023] leads to a completely connected space (even across differing numbers of reticulation events), so future work will thus involve updating the move set so that the space is connected.

S7 Finding optimal α and c for the simulated annealing algorithm

The cooling schedule is a crucial component of the simulated annealing algorithm, and the initial values of the control parameters α and c in Equation (6) in the main text must be specified prior to the network search. While [Salter and Pearl, 2001] reported that $\alpha = c = 0.5$ seemed to work well when searching the space of phylogenetic trees, the effect of these parameters when searching the space of phylogenetic networks is unknown. Using simulations under a simple scenario, we explore the effect of α and c in terms of efficiency and accuracy when searching the network space.

We selected a network topology shown in Fig. S1a as a model to generate data. We used the same edge lengths as in Figure S1a and set $\gamma = 0.4$ for the reticulation edge between species 4 and 5 and $\theta = 0.02$. We generated 10^5 gene trees using MS [Hudson, 2002] (i.e., 0.4×10^5 for one of the displayed trees that forms a cherry with species 4 and 5 and 0.6×10^5 for the other), followed by the simulation of DNA sequences using SEQ-GEN [Rambaut and Grass, 1997] under the JC69 model with a length of 100 b.p. per locus. All sequences were formatted using GOALIGN (<https://github.com/fredericlemoine/goalign>) and SNP-SITES [Page et al., 2016].

We selected $\alpha, c \in \{0.01, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9, 0.99\}$, producing 121 combinations for evaluation. For each pair of α and c , 20 independent runs were executed using the simulated annealing algorithm in PHYNEST. We used the same dataset for all evaluations and independent runs. We initiated the search using a random starting topology with the correctly specified outgroup taxon and $h_{max} = 1$. The maximum number of steps for each run was set to 10^3 to prevent an unnecessarily prolonged search. At the completion of each independent run, we recorded the number of steps taken and determined if the true network was reconstructed. For each pair of α and c , we computed the efficiency-accuracy score (F) using:

$$F = \frac{K}{\bar{W}} \quad (3)$$

where \bar{W} is the average number of steps, and K is the number of times the inferred final network is isomorphic to the true network out of the 20 runs. We interpreted higher values of F to indicate greater efficiency, as the true network is inferred with fewer steps.

Fig. S8: (a) Each box plot summarizes the number of steps taken at the termination of the 20 independent runs for each combination of α and c during network search using the simulated annealing algorithm. We selected $\alpha, c \in \{0.01, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9, 0.99\}$. The left y-axis represents the number of steps and ranges from 0 to 1000 (threshold). The x-axis represents tested values of α , and the value in the gray boxes on the right y-axis represents c . The red solid horizontal line in each pane indicates 500 steps. (b) Line graphs showing the computed F score using Equation (3) for the combinations of α and c . The y-axis on the left represents the F scores and the x-axis and right y-axis represent tested values of α and c , respectively. The horizontal red line in each pane indicates the score of 0.05.

Figure S8a summarizes the number of steps at the termination of each run for various combinations of α and c . Generally, the number of steps is inversely proportional to both α and c (i.e., more steps are required for smaller α and c). The search almost always required the maximum number of steps when $c = 0.01$ for $\alpha < 0.99$, $c = 0.1$ when $\alpha < 0.7$, and $c = 0.2$ when $\alpha < 0.2$. In most of these cases, the search ended because the maximum number of steps was reached, not because it converged to an optimum; thus, a higher threshold may be necessary when using smaller values of α and c . The search never required 10^3 steps when

$\alpha = 0.99$ regardless of c , and the search required approximately 78 steps on average when $\alpha = c = 0.99$. The search required fewer than 500 steps when $\alpha < 0.2$ with $c < 0.3$.

Figure S8b summarizes F scores using Equation (3) for each pair of α and c . The scores were arguably low when $\alpha \leq 0.7$ but were highest when $c = 0.9$ with $\alpha = 0.8$ and 0.9 . However, it is difficult to make a concrete generalization based on the evaluations conducted here because of the stochastic nature of the network search process. Also, our evaluation is based only on a very simple scenario, and extensive evaluation using various scenarios is needed. In practice, it is strongly recommended that users set α and c to relatively low values (e.g., $\alpha = c = 0.5$) with a large maximum number of steps, depending on the dataset size and the availability of computational resources, to increase their chances of finding the global optimum.

S8 Gene tree estimation errors for simulation study

Table S3 provides the mean gene tree estimation error (GTEE) for each g (i.e., number of gene trees in the input) in the simulation studies in the main text, using the scenarios \mathcal{N}_1 and \mathcal{N}_2 (Figure 2a and 2b, respectively, in the main text), as well as their averages. The mean GTEE is the normalized Robinson-Foulds (RF) distance between the true (i.e., simulated) and estimated gene trees, averaged across all loci. We used the Python package FASTMULRFS (<https://github.com/ekmolloy/fastmulrfs>) for this task. The GTEE observed here is considered a moderate to high estimate error based on [Molloy and Warnow, 2018].

Table S3: Mean gene tree estimation error for each g (i.e., number of gene trees in the input) and their averages for the scenarios \mathcal{N}_1 and \mathcal{N}_2 (Figure 2a and 2b, respectively, in the main text).

g	100	500	1000	3000	5000	Mean
\mathcal{N}_1	0.354	0.344	0.345	0.348	0.347	0.347
\mathcal{N}_2	0.402	0.402	0.407	0.406	0.403	0.404

S9 Accuracy of parameter estimation

This section presents results concerning the accuracy of parameter estimates for a network (τ, γ, θ) that are optimized by maximizing the composite likelihood function (Equation (2) in the main text). Here, the network topology is fixed to the true topology on which the data was generated (i.e., topology is not estimated simultaneously), and the relevant parameters are optimized using the fixed topology. We considered the two hybridization scenarios in Figure S1. We refer to Figure S1a as Scenario 1 and Figure S1b as Scenario 2 hereafter.

Let the speciation times τ_j in each scenario be indexed in a postorder traversal $j = 1, 2, \dots, n + h - 1$, where n is the number of tips and h is the number of reticulation vertices. The speciation times in Scenario 1 were set in coalescent units (CU) as $\tau_1 = \tau_2 = 1.5$, $\tau_3 = 3$, $\tau_4 = 5$, and $\tau_5 = 10$. Similarly, for Scenario 2, the speciation times were set as $\tau_1 = \tau_2 = \tau_3 = \tau_4 = 1.5$, $\tau_5 = \tau_6 = 3$, $\tau_7 = 5$, and $\tau_8 = 10$. We set $\gamma = 0.5$ for

every reticulation, and $\theta = 0.02$. For both scenarios, we simulated g gene trees where $g \in \{500, 1000, 5000, 10000\}$ using MS. We additionally simulated $g = 20000$ for Scenario 2 since more data may be required for accurate parameter estimation in a larger and more complex scenario. We decomposed Scenarios 1 and 2 into an array of displayed trees and simulated $0.5g$ and $0.25g$ gene trees for each displayed tree in Scenarios 1 and 2, respectively. The simulated gene trees were then used as input to simulate DNA sequences using SEQ-GEN with a length of 100 b.p. per locus under the JC69 model. We used 100 replicates for each g .

Fig. S9: (a) Boxplots that show $\hat{\tau}/\tau$ (left y-axis), the ratio of estimated τ (i.e., $\hat{\tau}$) to the true τ for different dataset sizes for Scenario 1 and (d) Scenario 2. The y-axis on the right shows the number of gene trees g in the data. The red horizontal line indicates $\hat{\tau}/\tau = 1$ (i.e., the estimate and the true values are identical). (b) Boxplots that show the estimates of the inheritance probability (γ ; y-axis) for Scenario 1 and (e) Scenario 2, for different sized datasets (x-axis in (b) and gray boxes on the right y-axis in (e)). On the x-axis of (e), γ_1 represents the probability associated with hybrid taxon 2 (i.e., the γ assigned to the reticulation edge between species 1 and species 2), and γ_2 represents the probability associated with hybrid taxon 5 (i.e., the γ assigned to the reticulation edge between species 4 and species 5). The red horizontal line indicates $\gamma = 0.5$, the true value. (c) Boxplots that show the estimates of the effective population size parameter (θ ; y-axis) that optimizes the composite likelihood function for Scenario 1 and (f) Scenario 2, for different sized datasets (x-axis). The red horizontal line indicates $\theta = 0.02$, the true value of θ .

Figure S9 presents estimates of τ , γ , and θ for various g in Scenario 1 (Fig. S9a–c, respectively) and Scenario 2 (Fig. S9d–f, respectively). In Figures S9a and S9d, we compute $\frac{\hat{\tau}}{\tau}$, the ratio of estimated τ (i.e., $\hat{\tau}$) to the true τ , to enhance readability. Here, $\frac{\hat{\tau}}{\tau} < 1$ represents τ being underestimated, and vice versa. For all estimates in both scenarios, $\frac{\hat{\tau}}{\tau}$ becomes closer to one, and the variance between the replicates is reduced as g increases. The estimates of γ (Fig. S9b and S9e) and θ (Fig. S9c and S9f) are close to the true value for all g . We omitted two replicates for Scenario 2 when $g = 500$ as their estimates seemed erroneous ($\hat{\tau} > 2000$ CU and $\theta \approx 0.0$). At this point, the exact reason for this behavior is unclear, although insufficient signal in the data might be responsible, as it never occurred when $g > 500$. Even in these cases, however, the estimates of γ for each reticulation were reasonably accurate, with $(\gamma_1, \gamma_2) = (0.56, 0.61)$ for one of the omitted replicates and $(0.59, 0.62)$ for the other.

S10 Mean computational times for the simulation study

Table S4: Mean computational time (measured in minutes) for each of the four methods evaluated (PHYLONET, SNAQ, PHYNEST using hill climbing (PHYNEST_HC), and PHYNEST using simulated annealing (PHYNEST_SA) for each number of loci in the dataset (g) using the network scenario \mathcal{N}_1 (Fig. 2a in the main text).

Scenario	\mathcal{N}_1					Mean
g	100	500	1000	3000	5000	
SNAQ	0.085	0.069	0.063	0.065	0.076	0.072
PHYLONET	0.375	0.362	0.365	0.4	0.434	0.387
PHYNEST_HC	0.385	0.33	0.354	0.544	0.405	0.404
PHYNEST_SA	16.433	13.467	14.295	16.673	16.258	15.425

Table S5: Mean computational time (measured in minutes) for each of the four methods evaluated for various g using the network scenario \mathcal{N}_2 (Fig. 2b in the main text).

Scenario	\mathcal{N}_2					Mean
g	100	500	1000	3000	5000	
SNAQ	2.581	2.908	3.351	2.848	4.489	3.235
PHYLONET	2.847	2.862	2.675	2.79	2.743	2.783
PHYNEST_HC	11.109	13.077	14.368	15.621	15.111	13.857
PHYNEST_SA	1317.565	1622.439	1857.167	1967.442	2037.756	1759.874

S11 Performance of PhyNEST in the absence of reticulation

Here we show that PHYNEST performs well in the absence of reticulation (i.e., species tree estimation). Following the data simulation procedure described in the main text, we generated 3×10^3 gene trees and a sequence alignment of 250 b.p. per locus using the three tree scenarios shown in Figure S10 below. These scenarios have the same topology but different branch lengths to vary the amount of ILS between them. We name the three scenarios in Figure S10a, b, and c as ‘no’, ‘ez’, and ‘df’, respectively, since Figure S10a is expected to have none or minimal ILS, Figure S10b to have a moderate amount of ILS, and Figure S10c to have the most ILS among the three scenarios. These scenarios can be written in Newick format as:

- no: (1:10.5,((2:3.0,(3:1.5,4:1.5):1.5):3.0,(((5:1.5,6:1.5):1.5,7:3.0):1.5,(8:1.5,9:1.5):3.0):1.5):4.5);,
- ez: (1:9.1,((2:3.0,(3:1.5,4:1.5):1.5):1.6,(((5:1.5,6:1.5):1.5,7:3.0):0.1,(8:1.5,9:1.5):1.6):1.5):4.5);,
- df: (1:7.7,((2:3.0,(3:1.5,4:1.5):1.5):0.2,(((5:1.5,6:1.5):1.5,7:3.0):0.1,(8:1.5,9:1.5):1.6):0.1):4.5);.

For each simulated dataset, we estimated a network with PHYNEST assuming $h_{max} = 0$ and $h_{max} = 1$ using hill climbing. One hundred replicates were performed.

Fig. S10: Three scenarios were used for data generation to evaluate PHYNEST on data generated under a species tree. Note that all three scenarios have the same topology, but the lengths of some branches differ. Data generated using a) is expected to have the smallest amount of incomplete lineage sorting (ILS), followed by b), with c) expected to have the largest amount of ILS. We name a), b), and c) as ‘no’, ‘ez’, and ‘df’, respectively.

Fig. S11: Performance of PHYNEST using data evolved along the species trees in Figure S10. The x-axis represents the three scenarios shown in Figure S10, labeled a), b), and c) as ‘no’, ‘ez’, and ‘df’, respectively. Plots a) and b) show the topological error measured by the Robinson-Foulds (RF) distance between the true and the estimated tree when $h_{max} = 0$ and the estimated network when $h_{max} = 1$, respectively. Plot c) shows the estimated γ value for the major reticulation edge in the networks estimated using $h_{max} = 1$.

Figure S11 summarizes the results. Our findings generally show that PHYNEST estimates the species tree topology accurately, even when the amount of ILS is high. When $h = 0$, PHYNEST reconstructed the true topology (i.e., the Robinson-Foulds (RF) distance between the topology on which the data were generated and the estimated topology equals zero) in all analyses except for one replicate in ‘df’. Similarly, when $h = 1$, the major tree (the displayed tree with higher probability) was always the true tree, except for one replicate in ‘df’. When the amount of ILS was small or moderate, the γ value for the major tree was generally very high (i.e., $\gamma > 0.9$). However, when the amount of ILS was high, γ fluctuated, ranging from 0.6 to 0.9. This fluctuation is possibly due to the increase in phylogenetic signal resulting from the high level of ILS that does not match the species tree which makes precise estimation of γ more challenging.

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